

The Human Format

We are a social species consisting of cooperating, autonomous individuals. 'Autonomous' in our context means that we each have minds of our own that dictate our behaviour. 'Cooperating' is an umbrella word that includes competition.

Our mastery of the environment and biological success resulted from an evolutionary break-through: communication by language. The brain of our primate ancestor evolved into our language-brain.

Each individual is unique and autonomous and possesses an all-important mental identity. The identity is acquired, not inherited.

Social interaction, *not* genetic determinism, creates each individual identity and hence the diversity of identities. This mental diversity is the source of the creativity of the species.

The identity is formed by 'social construction', which of course includes family interactions.

The 'constructor' of the identity, the constructor of the mind, is language. The 'mind' is the activity of the brain when handling language.

The human mind is language and nothing but language and therefore what can be a mind is dictated by:

- 1 The properties of language
- 2 The demands of meaningful communication
- 3 How the brain handles and stores language-based information

A 'natural language' is whatever works reliably in communication between human beings. A refined natural language consists of three elements: symbols, narrative and context. Symbols can be thought of as constructions that serve as points of agreed meaning in the flow of a narrative; their historical construction is ignored, facilitating their instantly recognised meaning. Narrative is a form of movement that enchains symbols into meaningful communication. Context is crucial because narrative and symbols in one context can have a different meaning in another context.

Meaningful communication is the result of agreement about meanings reached through negotiation, argument, and indeed copying. This continual negotiation is necessary because communication is taking place between individuals with different identities that provide different contexts for communicated information. To be 'meaningful', communication must influence behaviour in some way - which does not

imply that it is necessarily true or that it describes material reality. Nevertheless, meaningful communication is always real because to be meaningful it must be incorporated into some form of behaviour.

The large human brain is a language-brain and 'intelligence' is the by-product of language skills. The function of a brain is to keep its owner safe and thriving. The function of the *human* brain is to keep its owner both physically and *socially* safe and thriving. The indicator of paramount importance for the psychological well-being of individuals is their status in relation to others and this is an inevitable consequence of being members of a social species consisting of uniquely different individuals.